

ORGANIZATION OF THE LEARNING PROCESS AND
DEVELOPMENTAL ENVIRONMENT OF PRESCHOOL EDUCATIONAL
INSTITUTIONS BASED ON THE IDEA OF THE CHILD'S PERSONAL
DEVELOPMENT

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Abstract: This thesis analyzes the issues of organizing the educational process of preschool educational institutions based on the ideas of the child's personal development. The scientific and methodological foundations of forming a developmental educational environment, taking into account the individual characteristics of children, their abilities and needs, are highlighted. The thesis presents pedagogical approaches, interactive and innovative methods that affect the development of preschool education, as well as practical recommendations for increasing their effectiveness. The main principles of designing educational programs aimed at supporting the cognitive, emotional and social development of children are indicated.

Keywords: preschool education, personal development of the child, formation of a developmental environment, educational process, pedagogical approaches, innovative methods, individual development, organization of an educational environment.

Introduction

Each child is a separate world, a source of unique abilities, dreams and opportunities. Their natural potential is formed and developed in childhood. Therefore, creating a favorable environment for the comprehensive development of the child's personality in preschool educational institutions is one of the most important tasks of society. An individual approach to each child, understanding his needs and interests, and forming an educational system that allows them to learn and develop freely has become one of the main goals of educational institutions today.

The development of a child's personality is not limited to acquiring knowledge, but also plays an important role in his social, emotional and creative growth. This process requires the joint efforts of the teacher, parents and society. From this point of view, the educational process in preschool

educational institutions should form not only an educational, but also a developing environment.

In today's globalization and digital era, the opportunities for introducing innovative approaches to the educational process and revealing the inner potential of each child through the organization of a developmental educational environment are expanding. This requires a new approach to the educational process and increased attention to the child's personal development. In this regard, creating a favorable developmental environment for children is important not only for their future successful life, but also for the sustainable development of society as a whole.

Methodology

To support the comprehensive development of the child's personality, methodological approaches used in preschool education should have a specific scientific basis. The main criterion in this process is the creation of an appropriate educational environment for the child, taking into account his personal abilities, needs and pace of development. Therefore, the research methodology is based on child-centered approaches and is focused on finding individualized paths of development.

In this thesis, three main methodological approaches were used to organize an educational environment to ensure the personal development of children. The first is a scientific and pedagogical analysis, which studies best practices and theoretical foundations for creating a developmental environment in the preschool education system. The second is innovative approaches, which involve stimulating independent thinking in children through the use of developmental game methods, interactive technologies, and creative activity methods. The third approach is practical and experimental work, that is, various pedagogical tools were used to ensure the active participation of children in the educational process and assess the results of their development.

The design of the educational process was based on construction, developmental games, and interactive tools designed for cognitive development. At the same time, the methodological study also studied the opinions of parents and educators, and factors that positively affect the development of the child were identified.

As a result, the importance of a systematic and creative approach to creating a developmental environment that is consistent with the child's personal development in preschool education was determined as the main principle of the methodology. This approach is not only for use in the

educational process, but also an effective tool for creating a successful foundation for the child's future life.

Discussion

The issues of the development of the child's personality and his adaptation to the educational process in a preschool educational institution have always been of central importance in the educational process. During this study, the impact and practical results of organizing a developmental environment were discussed. It was found that the educational environment created to develop the individual abilities of children not only satisfies their psychological and emotional needs, but also enhances their social activity.

During the discussion, it became clear that the main aspect of a developmental educational environment is the creation of comfortable, safe and stimulating conditions for the child for creative activity. In particular, through game activities and interactive methods, children's activity and interests increase significantly. At the same time, it was confirmed that the existence of the necessary conditions for children to express themselves, develop independent thinking and problem-solving skills in the educational process is important.

The results of the experiment showed that the personal development of a child is not limited only to the skills and approach of the teacher. The participation of parents and the community also plays a major role in this process. In particular, the study showed that activities carried out in collaboration with parents further enhanced the success of children in the educational process. Seminars, trainings and consultations held with parents in educational institutions made it possible to more effectively manage the child's development process.

Also, some problems were identified during the discussion. For example, the lack of innovative tools and methods necessary for a developmental environment in all educational institutions or the existence of gaps in the knowledge and skills of teachers in their application was noted as a problematic aspect. In order to solve these problems, the need to constantly involve teachers in advanced training courses and provide preschool educational institutions with modern tools was emphasized.

In conclusion, the development environment and the proper organization of the educational process play an important role in ensuring the personal development of a child. For the effective implementation of this process, parents,

educators and leaders of the education system must work together. Only in this way will each child be able to fully realize their potential.

Conclusion

The development of a child's personality is an important process that affects the sustainable development of not only the education system, but also the entire society. By creating a developmental environment in preschool educational institutions, each child will have the opportunity to demonstrate their natural abilities and talents. Proper organization of this process allows you to support not only the cognitive potential of children, but also their social and emotional development.

The results of the study show that the effectiveness of a developmental educational environment largely depends on the skills of educators, cooperation with parents and the implementation of innovative approaches to the educational process. The use of game activities, creative activities and interactive methods in educational institutions helps children expand their worldview, develop independent thinking and problem-solving skills.

At the same time, one of the important factors for the development of a child's personality is the creation of a comfortable and safe environment. The developmental environment enhances children's interest in learning and directly affects their success in the educational process. For the effective implementation of this process, it is necessary not only to improve pedagogical approaches, but also to develop the material and technical base of educational institutions.

Thus, supporting the personal development of a child in preschool education requires an integrated approach to the educational process. Through the integral cooperation of educational institutions, parents and society, it is possible to create an opportunity for each child to fully realize their abilities. This serves as a solid foundation not only for the future successful life of the child, but also for the sustainable development of society as a whole.

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